

Design and Development of Replacement of existing Timer card with PLC based Logic

Milan K. Gangani¹, Ravi J. Mistri², Ishan P. Patel³, Prof. Jignesh G. Bhatt⁴, and Amit M. Dholakia⁵

¹Department of Instrumentation and Control Engineering, Faculty of Technology, Dharmsinh Desai University, Nadiad, India
Email: milan100196@gmail.com

²Department of Instrumentation and Control Engineering, Faculty of Technology, Dharmsinh Desai University, Nadiad, India
Email: mistriravij@gmail.com

³Department of Instrumentation and Control Engineering, Faculty of Technology, Dharmsinh Desai University, Nadiad, India
Email: ishan1195@gmail.com

⁴Department of Instrumentation and Control Engineering, Faculty of Technology, Dharmsinh Desai University, Nadiad, India
Email: jigneshgbhatt@gmail.com

⁵Instrumentation Department, S&PG Plant, Gujarat Narmada Valley Fertilizers and Chemicals Limited, Bharuch, India
Email: amdholakia@gnfc.in

Abstract— Ash handling plant is playing crucial part in removing carbon particles and thereby preventing environmental pollution, by removing ash from flue gas using Electro Static Precipitator (ESP) and collecting it into a silo. For safety purpose, air should be evacuated using bag filter, which should be periodically cleaned by sequential operation of Solenoid Operated Valves (SOVs) controlled by electronic timer card. The work presented includes study of existing timer card based scheme, related problems and its replacement by Programmable logic controller (PLC) based scheme. Unlike existing timer card based scheme, the new PLC based scheme includes compressors running signal as a feedback and in addition of resolving associated problems, it also improves overall operability, controllability and functionality.

Keywords—Automation, Instrumentation, Control system, Programmable Logic Controller, Timer sequence control

I. INTRODUCTION[1-3]

This section includes the basic overview of the work carried out along with brief outline of the remaining paper. After combustion process, outgoing flue gases from boiler contains solid particles of carbon which are collected as ash using Electro Static Precipitator (ESP). After collection, the ash could be handled in two ways. First, dry ash could be sold to cement manufacturing companies and second, ash could be dumped into pond in slurry form by mixing it with water.

In the first dry ash method, ash has been transported using pressurized air and evacuated in atmosphere to protect intermediate silo from bursting out. Prior to this, air has been filtered out using bag filter situated on the silo top. To clean the filter, 10 Solenoid Operated Valves (SOVs) have been installed, actuating in a preset timed sequence to blow out compressed air. Using electronic timer card, SOVs have been operated every 5 seconds for particular ON/OFF timings

adjustable locally from field by potentiometer on timer card.

The paper begins with the section containing introductory details followed by problem statement and proposed solution in sections II and III with brief details of utilized hardware and software in section IV. Section V includes details of design and implementation along with flow chart and snapshots of PLC ladder logic developed. Section-VI presents results obtained along with interesting discussions. Finally, the paper ends with useful conclusions with list of references cited to mark the end of the paper.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

To replace existing electronic timer cards with PLC based logic, by design-development, testing-validation and implementation has been problem statement of this work.

Existing electronic timer card based sequence and logic execution had limitations such as frequent failures due to deposition of dry ash, bad connection contacts, effects of changing weather, poor functionality and hence lesser reliability. Further, physical presence of an operator in the field was required for modification in timings in timer card, which was inconvenient, involving manual intervention as well as compromising safety. Comparatively, PLC based timer would be superior, free from frequent maintenance and hence with higher reliability. Further, availability of already existing Siemens' S7-400 PLC with spare capacity available reduces cost implication considerably.

III. PROPOSED SOLUTION

PLC being fully digital and microcontroller based, enjoys numerous advantages over electronic timer card, such as higher reliability, better functionality, rich instruction set, higher operability, higher speed and accuracy. Siemens make PLC S7-400 has already been available in control room of the plant with spare I/O capacity. Therefore, without much cost implication, replacement of existing electronic timer card was proposed by PLC as a solution of the problem identified.

IV. HARDWARE AND SOFTWARE[4]

A. Hardware

Siemens' Simatic S7-400 model PLC, consisting of I/O cards and Human Interface Station (HIS) and 10 SOVs have been major hardware utilized in development of the work presented.

B. Software

Siemens' Simatic S7 software has been used to develop ladder program to control timer based SOV sequence.

V. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

A. Flow Chart

Initial Condition for starting the sequence is that one of the compressors (C1 or C2) should be running. The sequence could be started by pressing START push button and stopped by pressing the STOP push button anytime or after completion of cycle. System will keep on checking the compressors' output, until and unless any one of the compressor is on. When START button is pressed and both the compressor are not in running conditions, then timer based SOVs sequence to be executed for 10 minutes.

Figure 1 Flow chart of PLC ladder logic[1-4]

B. PLC ladder logic development[1-4]

- (i) (Network44): Initial Condition for starting the sequence is that one of the compressors C1 or C2 should be running. For checking that one memory bit is used.
- (ii) (Network45): When START button is pressed and both the compressor is not in running status then SOVs sequence should work for 10 minutes.
- (iii) (Network46): When START (DB40.DBX0.0) button is pressed the sequence should be started. When STOP (invert DB40.DBX0.0) button is pressed the sequence should be stopped after completion of that cycle.
- (iv) (Network47): For SOVs sequence timing, 2 timers are used. One timer is for how much time SOVs are operated and another one is for generating delay between two SOV operations. So, ON Delay timer used is of 5s and 200ms.
- (v) (Network49): Number of execution is counted.
- (vi) (Network50-60): When Counter value reaches as stored in Comparator along with every SOV Output bit, SOV operates sequentially.
- (vii) (Network48): After operation of last SOV, one reset bit is generated. This bit resets the counter, timer and again sequence operates from first SOV. This sequence run until Stop button is pressed.

Figure 2 PLC ladder logic design[1-4]

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Results

After replacement of PLC in place of electronic timer card, numerous benefits have been observed, out of which three major benefits have been included below:

(i) Improved reliability

Chances of having failure in loop are greatly reduced due to inherent rugged design of PLC and its

installation away from dusty environment. Further, potential-free contacts of PLC have reduced chances of sparks generation and possible accidents, failure due to short circuit problems as well as earthing related issues.

(ii) Better functionality

As compared to electronic timer card, expansion of PLC is simple, easy and quicker as it requires only addition and activation of more I/O cards only with little modification in ladder software.

Further, due to availability of HIS, live real-time view and troubleshooting have also been facilitated.

(iii) Higher operability

Proposed modified PLC based design provides more flexible and convenient user operation from control room as compared to field based operation in earlier case. Operators could conveniently modify timings in the SOV sequences with higher accuracy and effectiveness.

Higher resolution due to PLC in timing settings has also improved overall accuracy of the operation.

Prior to implementation simulation facility availed on PLC has resulted into better insights before making final decisions.

B. Discussions

In the earlier situation, when electronic timer card was used in loop, there were many problem associated with it such as, requirement of operator's physical presence in field to change timing settings, which involved inconvenient manual intervention and compromises operator's safety. Variations in ambient conditions were adversely affecting operational functionality of timer card. Frequent failures due to deposition of dry ash resulted in poor functionality and hence lesser reliability.

Replacement of electronic timer card by PLC, not only resulted in resolving all the above mentioned problems, but also provided advantages like facilitation of convenient

modification in timing settings by operator from control room without going into the field, thereby removing inconvenient manual intervention as well as large reduction in losses of productions on account of frequent faults in timer card.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

Replacement of existing timer card by PLC logic has enhanced overall reliability and controllability due to inherent rugged and trustworthy design of PLC over electronic timer circuit. Overall operational safety and accuracy have also found improved. The transformation has been completed without much cost implication due to usage of existing PLC with spare capacity in the plant.

VIII. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

All the authors hereby acknowledge with sincere thanks help, cooperation and support received from Management and Office bearers of Gujarat Narmada Valley Fertilizers and Chemicals (GNFC) Limited, Bharuch and Dharmsinh Desai University (DDU), Nadiad.

IX. REFERENCE

- [1] Plant manual, S&PG Plant, Gujarat Narmada valley Fertilizers and Chemicals (GNFC) Limited, Bharuch, Gujarat, India.
- [2] Bag filter (Relay Output) [ONLINE] data available at http://kanaelectromechs.com/products/bfc_ro.asp#page=page-1.
- [3] Solenoid operated valve [ONLINE] available at https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Solenoid_valve
- [4] SIEMENS SIMATIC Ladder Logic (LAD) for S7-300 and S7-400 Programming Reference Manual